

Working out the kinks: Statistical constraints and Millennium Development Goal evaluation

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Abstract

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) have been set up for measurability and accountability. With their deadline now passed, pre- and post-treatment results can be evaluated according to the way the MDGs and their indicators have been set up. However, statistical constraints in the form of availability, quality, and predictive ability create roadblocks. This paper explores the possibilities and challenges of evaluating the MDGs using MDG 3, gender equality and women's empowerment, as its focus. It starts by using the MDGs as a natural experiment in sub-Saharan Africa, testing for structural breaks and kinks, showing that although geared towards this style of evaluation, the MDG architecture falls short of its goal. It then addresses the statistical roadblocks for doing so and separates the theoretical from the practical uses of the MDGs' indicator-based structure. It argues for greater consideration of the framing effects of indicators, as they shape understanding of a problem and potential solutions. While MDG indicators were built for measurement, the way they frame issues may have more important implications for empirical evaluation.

Keywords – data for development; gender equality; politics of data; evidence-based policymaking

1 Introduction

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the eight global goals set by the United Nations meant to serve the needs of the world's poor, were meant to signify a commitment to equity and inclusion (Ki-moon, 2011). The third MDG (MDG 3) is aimed specifically at women, promoting gender equity and women's empowerment through targeting gender inequalities in education, non-agricultural employment, and national parliaments. This lofty and noble goal has been set for every country with the aim to achieve it by 2015. If achieved, it would mark a crucial starting point in the fight against discriminatory social institutions biased against women. It is an ongoing for sub-Saharan African countries, the central focus of this study, where gender-based discrimination is a pervasive

societal issue and creates barriers to women's education and participation in politics and the labour market.

What were the actual results of these goals? As this paper will show, using the MDGs as a significant moment for promoting gender equality has limited discernible results in sub-Saharan African countries. Statistical constraints hinder the evaluation of the MDGs, rendering theoretically sound quasi-experimentation far less useful in practice. Constraints like low predictive ability, stemming from poor data quality and limited availability, can create serious problems for indicator-based projects like the MDGs. Such barriers to evaluation are at odds with how the MDGs were set up, as the design lent itself to pre- versus post-treatment style testing. Due to these issues, this paper argues that MDG indicators have resulted in acting more as framing devices than as strictly tools of measurement and benchmarking. In other words, they have value to the extent that they frame our understanding of an issue area, such as gender equality, and thus guide policy prescriptions. While this argument is rooted in the analysis for sub-Saharan African countries, gaps in MDG data availability and quality can be found worldwide (see Chen et al., 2013).

Statistical constraints in measuring and evaluating the MDGs are of particular concern in the sub-Saharan African context (see Jerven, 2013), the focus on this work. Despite these challenges, there is value in running MDG evaluation per its own design and to evaluate its evaluation in addition to using this case to explore the incentives for measurement. Could the MDGs have driven progress towards better data collection? In effect, part of the success of the MDGs was the increase in data availability, even in countries with low statistical capacity. Though this success may be modest, it is a promising result of the MDGs with implications for the post-2015 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

This work takes a regression discontinuity approach to evaluating the MDG evaluation method, laying out the

model and results.¹ It analyzes the results on their own and in the context of the predictive ability of the data, which is uneven at best. The MDGs are shown, however, to have had a measurably impact on data collection. The full version of this paper includes the full set of results, in addition to more background material on MDG 3 in sub-Saharan Africa. This discussion paper instead focuses on the discussion of the issues presented by data availability and quality, setting the stage for the argument that an indicator's main value should be seen as a framing tool rather than a measurement tool. This discussion highlights why the political nature of the MDG structure needs to be considered when evaluating outcomes. The full version of the paper engages also with the implications for the SDGs.

2 Background

2.1 The Millennium Development Goals

The United Nations' MDGs represent a global anti-poverty campaign based on eight goals. The goals received board national-level support with state governments signing on to the associated Millennium Declaration in 2000, with the aim of achieving the goals by 2015. Each goal has one or more associated targets. These targets make the goals' aspirations more tangible. Indicators form the level below targets, encapsulating measurability of progress. For example, MDG 3 is comprised of:

Goal: Promote gender equality and empower women

Target: Eliminate gender disparity in primary and secondary education, preferably by 2005, and in all levels of education no later than 2015.

Indicator 3.1: Ratios of girls to boys in primary, secondary and tertiary education

Indicator 3.2: Share of women in wage employment in the non-agricultural sector

Indicator 3.3: Proportion of seats held by women in national parliament (UNSD, 2008)

The creators of the MDGs took broad aspirations, like gender equality in this case, and translated them into specific, measurable numbers in the indicators. Underlying the indicators are normative viewpoints on how to best solve the problem the goal presents. The aim of MDG 3 is to promote women's empowerment, with the target and primary indicator focused on gender parity in education. The implication is that women's education is an important component of women's empowerment and gender equality.

The indicator communicates this as a preferred approach to empowering women, with the effect of encouraging policymakers to focus on it over other measures.

The MDGs have been constructed using goals and targets unconstrained by strict policy prescriptions. Setting targets and standards for development is a useful tool for global governance organizations as it sets a global agenda while leaving states to autonomously produce their own internal policies. The way in which a global governance institution influences national policy is increasingly important given what Jakobi (2009) describes as the rise of global public policy, where education and other policy fields increasingly look to international actors for direction. Education policy in particular has been rescaled to the international level, with global policy discourses disseminated through global education policy networks influencing national policy production and providing incentives for states to work in new ways (Lingard & Rawolle, 2011). Verger et al. (2012) take this point further from a global governance perspective, arguing that in the field of education, global governance institutions are redefining the relationship between the state and education policy. By operating at different scales, they argue that non-state actors are increasing their presence and authority in the field of education policy as well as in other policy fields.

2.2 Criticism of the MDGs

At face value, it is commendable for the world to pursue an anti-poverty agenda. The MDGs, however, have faced a myriad of criticisms. In an overview of the limitations of the MDGs, Fehling, Nelson, and Venkatapuram (2013) describe many limitations inherent in the MDG framework. Shortfalls include over-simplicity, creation by few stakeholders, failure to include previously accepted development objectives, and quite simply the difficulty of actually achieving the goals. The UN has also recognized multiple barriers to progress, although many seem to originate outside of the UN system. Such barriers include lack of resources, lack of accountability, and low levels of commitment and interest (UN, 2010). MDG indicator selection has been criticized for being a closed-door exercise (Fukuda-Parr & Hulme, 2011; Hulme, 2009), selecting indicators focused on outcomes over process (Tsfaye & Wyant, 2016).

Some of the criticism of the MDGs also stems from a larger discussion around governance by indicators and measurement-driven approaches. Governance by indicators occurs when indicators are used to influence behaviour as well as resource production and distribution. This style of

¹ Available upon request.

governance, while seemingly objective, is inherently political. Values and norms sit at the core of indicators and their selection. This reality may be ignored during monitoring and evaluation, particularly when done within the system from which the indicators originate. The MDGs faced these challenges as a clear example of governance by indicators, as the UN looked to influence policy priorities and action through them. The Goals rested on an undercurrent of ‘what is measured, matters’ and ‘what is counted, counts’ towards a progress on a broad goal (see Best, 2014).

In addition, there is a range of criticism stemming from MDG evaluation due to the way the indicators and measurement framework were set up. There is debate about the quality of the MDGs as a measure of performance. Success according to the MDGs was based on a pass/fail binary focused on absolute relative change (see Clemens, Kenny, & Moss, 2004; Easterly, 2009), ignoring the pace of change (see Fukuda-Parr, Greenstein, & Stewart, 2013). Saith (2006) argues that the MDGs as a whole were poorly designed; in terms of evaluation, he argues that the Goals are methodological flawed, due in part to technical deficiencies and a lack of data. The dual criticism of the technical and the political natures of indicators indicates significant barriers for the MDGs to affect development and change.

MDG 3 has been the subject of a more specific range of critiques, from its underlying assumptions to its focus on outcomes. Connell (2010) identifies three assumptions underlying MDG 3 that have been seriously challenged: gender as an unproblematic binary, formal education as an unquestionable good, and targeting girls and women without strong inclusion of boys and men. North (2010) takes issue with how MDG 3 has taken the complicated idea of gender equality and reduced it to quantifiable targets based on gender equality in education. As a strategy for gender equality, Chismya et al. (2012) argue that MDG 3 alone is not enough to achieve gender equality or women’s empowerment because inequitable gender norms exist within and outside the education system. Further, they posit that (numerical) gender parity in the classroom does not necessarily translate directly into reducing gender-based discrimination in the community. Gender inequalities reflect societal norms affecting women throughout their lives and these norms are held by school actors including children themselves.

The MDGs’ approach to education in general has also been called into question. MDG 2, the goal of universal primary education, puts a primary measurement focus on

enrolment. None of the indicators strictly measure completion. The closest way to measure primary school completion is by accounting for the final-year enrolment rate of those enrolled at the start of primary school. In addition, the MDGs did not attempt to measure educational quality. None of the indicators, or the approach more broadly, address learning or competency (see Filmer, Hasan, & Pritchett, 2006). There may also be problems from a policy-making point of view. MDG 2 does not provide strict policy guidelines, only indicators of success, but education policy creation is difficult as there is no concrete list of policies or determinants of educational outcomes and few clear guidelines exist in the literature (World Bank, 2004). Bourguignon et al.’s report (2008) argues for a coherent policy framework between a country’s national development strategy and MDG-related strategy, noting that policymakers know more about what not to do than which policies should be used. These wide-ranging criticisms are important to keep in mind when trying to evaluate the MDGs, especially according to the MDGs’ own indicators.

3 Methodology, data, and results

In order to determine the effectiveness of MDG 3 in sub-Saharan Africa, it is useful to think of the MDGs as a form of intervention or treatment used in a natural experiment. The structure of the MDGs lends itself to this approach, with a potential disruption for development outcomes in the year 2000 and implying that changes at this time were as a result of the MDGs. Further, although the goals themselves are aspirations, the indicator-based framework was created for purposes of measurement and evaluation. The following model is used to test for regression discontinuities, both in terms of breaks and kinks:

$$\alpha_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 year + \beta_3 X_{it} + \beta_4 MDG + \beta_5 change + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where α is the relevant MDG 3 indicator, β_1 is the constant term, $year$ is the forcing variable (starting with 1985 = year 1), X is a set of control variables to account for existing conditions for women, MDG is the dummy variable indicating the treatment (testing for a break), and $change$ is a variable to account for the rate of change of the slope (testing for a kink). This model is tested controlling for country fixed effects.

The panel dataset includes 47 sub-Saharan African countries for years 1985 to 2015. Data has been primarily sourced from within the UN system, including the UN’s official MDG database as well as UNESCO and the World Bank. The only exception is the Cingranelli-Richards

² Other variables had been tested for inclusion, including measures for wealth, health, education, rural populations, and others. The model that only accounted for existing rights-based conditions for women had the best fit.

(CIRI) Human Rights Dataset (Cingranelli & Richards, 2013). The data sources for the MDG indicators were chosen intentionally to reflect what is used for evaluation within the UN system in order to assess the effectiveness of MDG 3 from a UN perspective. It is important to note that the dataset is not complete and that there are many gaps. This problem will be addressed throughout the results and discussion sections as it creates a significant barrier to evaluating MDG outcomes, although there was progress made towards better data collection and evaluation over the course of the MDGs.

Table 1. Results³

	Gender parity (primary)	Gender parity (secondary)	Gender parity (tertiary)	Non-agri wage labour	Seats in parliament
Year	0.003** * (0.000)	0.009*** (0.000)	0.010** * (0.000)	0.438*** (0.000)	0.013 (0.901)
Econ rights	0.013** (0.028)	0.024*** (0.004)	-0.0003 (0.981)	-0.533 (0.214)	1.046* (0.082)
Poli rights	-0.003 (0.548)	-0.032*** (0.000)	-0.002 (0.887)	0.120 (0.789)	3.708*** (0.000)
Social rights	- 0.026** *	-0.033*** (0.000)	0.001 (0.926)	0.091 (0.848)	1.561*** (0.005)
MDG	-0.056* (0.066)	0.061 (0.143)	-0.0464 (0.585)	4.955** (0.029)	- 13.739** *
Change	0.004** (0.012)	-0.005** (0.031)	0.004 (0.408)	-0.308** (0.034)	0.922*** (0.000)
Constant	0.798** * (0.000)	0.700*** (0.000)	0.367** * (0.000)	23.988** * (0.000)	-0.280 (0.858)
N	681	469	376	124	354

Note: *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1, standard errors in brackets

4 Data quality and availability

Poor data quality and availability is a core concern with the MDGs. It affects evaluation and prediction and undermines the quantitative foundation of the Goals. There are significant gaps in the datasets related to measures of women's rights and empowerment (from the CIRI dataset). This may be more understandable in the context of issues that are more difficult to measure, like norms and beliefs. However, there are also significant historical gaps for the specific MDG 3 indicators. For example, percentage of women in non-agricultural wage employment is listed as indicator 3.2. One may expect adequate documentation and data collection for an official indicator. In this dataset of 47 countries from 1985 to 2015, however, there are only 191 observations for this variable. Approximately 87% of these numbers are missing. With the MDGs making up half of

the timeframe used, there is a large amount of data missing in a time when the point is to measure progress. This lack of data creates a barrier to our understanding of what women face around the world and what policies work to help.

Missing data is nothing new. Bourguignon et al. (2008) have asserted that the majority of developing countries do not produce regular or reliable data. Jerven (2013) has widely argued that the statistical capacity in Africa is low and that the data produced can be misleading. The state of statistical capacity in these countries sets them at a disadvantage for indicator-based projects like the MDGs. When setting up this style of priority setting without addressing basic problems with gathering and analyzing these numbers, global social governance actors like the United Nations further set up developing countries for failure, or at least perceived failure. Potential for failure is further compounded by Jacob's (2017) findings that strong national-level measurement systems increased the probability of MDG success.

Jacob's (2017) finding can be read in a positive light, however, given the impact that the MDGs did have on data collection and availability. While data gaps remain and statistical capacity is uneven across the region, the MDGs did some see success in encouraging country-level measurement. Extending Easterly's (2009) arguments to this result reminds researchers to pay attention to relative changes and not to get caught up in pass/fail binary thinking. Further, it must be pointed out that the problems of measurement and evaluation that did persist throughout the MDGs have not gone unnoticed, from the forward-looking call for a data revolution to self-reflective reports like the *Lessons Learned from MDG Monitoring from A Statistical Perspective* from the United Nations Inter-Agency and Expert Group on MDG Indicators (2013). Productive awareness of the issue is critical for moving forward. So too is recognizing successes and building on them.

The fields of development and social policy as part of the wider global governance system, have seen the rise of evidence-based policy and an increasing reliance on indicators. This approach has been fostered in a quantitatively-minded system. Indicators and data have far-reaching influence, as the quantitatively-driven system has had a profound effect on how global social policy agendas are set. The goals of the MDGs and the SDGs, for example, are set on the foundation of predetermined indicators. While governance by indicators may be considered by some as a problematic governance approach (see, for example, Davis et al, 2012), it is clearly problematic to have data-driven projects without the data. Despite the progress shown here, more needs to be done. The purpose of the quantifiable nature of the goals'

³ Full description and analysis of these results are available in the full paper.

indicators is the ability to measure, monitor, evaluate, and the like. Without the necessary statistical capacity, however, actors at any level in the social governance and policy sphere cannot use indicators for this purpose.

5 Framing versus measurement

The inherent problems with MDG data in terms of (primarily historical) availability, quality, and predictive ability challenge the MDG indicators' goals of measurability and accountability. Data problems can then turn into problems for policy, process, and results when these indicators are used as guides. Indicators claim to measure progress towards a given target. Using these measurements, we can assess, evaluate, rank, and the like. The MDGs were designed for this purpose. It is assumed that the MDGs offer a measurement tool but fail to do so, in large part due to lack of historical data. Data collection did increase over the course of the MDGs but gaps remain.

Perhaps however indicators are better understood as a framing tool. In other words, indicators frame our understanding of an issue, generating priorities and policy prescriptions in line with the given frame (Fukuda-Parr, 2016). In this case, in order to achieve gender equality and to empower women, countries are encouraged to prioritize policies that get women and girls in school, in non-agricultural wage employment, and sitting in parliament. Whether or not these are the most effective or efficient policy routes is not part of the discussion. In addition, the MDGs' focus on indicators framed measurement as a key underlying issue, to some degree of success. The indicators thus shape our understanding and, given their presentation as scientific and objective (see Hansen & Porter, 2012), are taken as truth, the basis that guides future policy responses.

Understanding indicators as a framing tool is different from seeing them, or the goals generally, as 'aspirational prods'. The goals and indicators did inspire action and effort, nudging policymakers to tackle specific social priorities. The framing component goes a step further. Fukuda-Parr, Yamin, and Greenstein (2014) spell this out in their analysis of the MDG targets, arguing that the targets shaped understanding of development and how solutions were identified. Merry (2016) also points to the framing effect of indicators in relation to, as one example, measuring violence against women. She showed how defining the problem, in terms of how it was measured, implicitly identified the way to address the problem. In evaluating the MDGs, it is therefore important to understand this framing effect, especially when there may be a disconnect between a goal and the associated indicators. Thus, achieving MDG 3 does not strictly mean that gender equality has been achieved in a broad sense, only that it has been achieved according to a narrow definition or understanding derived from the indicators.

The framing versus measurement tool problem is akin to thinking treating a wrench as a hammer. You can use a wrench as if it were a hammer in order to bang a nail into a wall, but you are neither doing the job efficiently nor are you using the wrench in the way it was designed to work. With the MDGs, an indicator is being used to measure, which it has difficulty doing given current realities with statistical capacity constraints. This use also neglects how an indicator frames policy problems and solutions. When goals and indicators are not well-aligned or are overly narrow, the resultant framing can push us further away from the spirit of the goal.

Using indicators as a framing tool is not a problem in and of itself. It is also not an unknown or uncommon understanding of indicators, given burgeoning discussion on 'governance by indicators' and 'politics by numbers'. Much of this discussion, however, is happening outside of, but adjacent to, discussions of measurement issues within mainstream economic circles. Recognition of indicators as a framing, as opposed to a strict measurement, tool is what may be missing from quantitative analysis. The MDGs theoretically lend themselves to measurement but in practice they are unable to do so. Bridges need to be built outside of dominant economic approaches in order to holistically tackle problems inherent in MDG indicators. This is in part because an indicator's value as a framing device is important but so too is its value as a measurement device. In quantitatively-based evaluation, there is a need to recognize the usefulness of an indicator as a framing device but to push statistical capacity forward so it can also be used as a measurement tool, as was its initial purpose.

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